

THE ROLE OF SCIENTIFIC THINKING IN ENHANCING THE PHILOSOPHICAL OUTLOOK OF YOUTH

Nishonova Diyora Tursunovna

Farg'ona davlat universiteti mustaqil izlanuvchisi

Orcid: 0009-0003-8073-1910

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19229937>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 21st March 2026

Accepted: 23rd March 2026

Online: 25th March 2026

KEYWORDS

youth, scientific thinking, worldview, philosophical worldview, bibliotherapy, socio-philosophical factors, individual spirituality, social development, scientific worldview, concept, humanism

ABSTRACT

This article covers studying the socio-philosophical factors of using bibliotherapy in increasing the philosophical worldview of young people, the study of the content and conceptual foundations of increasing the philosophical worldview of young people, clarifying the role and possibilities of bibliotherapy in increasing the philosophical worldview of young people. Proposals and recommendations have also been developed on the tasks and prospects for using bibliotherapy to increase the philosophical worldview of young people in New Uzbekistan..

Introduction

In the educational process, it is not always possible to require learners to independently carry out all stages of an investigation. However, it is necessary to familiarize them with the structure of scientific investigations using examples from the history of science, reveal the logic behind these investigations, and demonstrate how scientists arrived at particular theoretical or experimental discoveries. It is important to explain which methods motivated scientists to engage in research, why specific problems were solved at particular stages of scientific development, and how these investigations were connected to the advancement of technology or the economy. This is essential for developing dialectical thinking among learners. For example, when studying the law of universal gravitation, it is necessary to discuss the process, explain the logic behind it, and clarify why Newton addressed this particular problem at that time.

As a first approach to developing scientific thinking, learners should be shown, in a comprehensible manner, how scientists first encountered hypotheses about the quantum description of energy emission and absorption when studying the quantum theory of light, what contradictions arose, and how they were resolved, including how the primacy of wave and corpuscular properties was established [1, 308].

The second approach involves engaging learners in solving educational problems: defining hypotheses, searching for ways to resolve problems, developing investigation plans, and designing research methodologies.

The third approach requires learners to identify cause-and-effect relationships, explain observed phenomena and the properties of objects, and work with idealized models.

The fourth approach is to develop learners' ability to draw conclusions based on the methods of induction and deduction. Learners should be gradually involved in making conclusions through deductive reasoning.

Literature Review and Methods

Numerous studies have addressed the role of scientific thinking in shaping youth cognition, the importance of reading for society and the individual, and the social and individual aspects of developing reading habits. In Uzbekistan, researchers such as E. Yoldosheva, A. Umarov, Yo. Qayumkhojaeva, B. Ganieva, A. Abdullaev, G. Amanova, U. Bek, H. Davron, and G. Shirinov have examined issues related to forming reading skills and habits in youth.

Among the scientists of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), S.I. Abakumova, A.V. Avdeeva, L.I. Belenkaya, G.I. Bondarenko, Ye.V. Buneeva, Ye.I. Golubeva, and M.A. Yumatova have studied methods of engaging youth in reading, developing reading skills and culture, and the particularities of traditional and modern reading technologies.

Foreign pedagogues and psychologists such as L. Hell, D. Ziegler, D. Fallows, K. Merga, A. Perrin, and D.F. Roberts have explored the axiological aspects of reading and book culture in countries such as the UK, France, Germany, and the USA, as well as the structural foundations and essential directions for enhancing reading culture among youth.

Results and Discussion

Systematic application of the discussed teaching methods ensures the structured development of competent scientific thinking among learners. For this purpose, a special system of knowledge must be designed that requires learners to draw deductive conclusions. Seminars foster general interest and debate, serving as an effective form of collaborative work. Each learner observes the clash of ideas, attempts to clarify their position, expresses their opinion, justifies and substantiates it, complements their thoughts, and arrives at a theoretical conclusion. This approach can also be applied in problem-solving and laboratory activities [2, 265].

Creativity represents the highest form of human activity and resilience. Creative abilities include the capacity to explain the necessity of innovations, formulate problems, apply necessary knowledge for advancing hypotheses, validate hypotheses theoretically and practically, and generate new, unique solutions by searching for ways to solve problems.

The development of creative abilities involves positive reinforcement in teaching, fostering interest in knowledge, cultivating skills based on deep and solid understanding, applying knowledge to explain phenomena, and integrating generalized academic and practical knowledge, skills, and competencies to support learners' independent development [3, 101]. The foundation of productive abilities lies in theoretical thinking and active knowledge engagement. During lessons, using question-and-answer sessions and problem-based methods is an effective means of developing learners' creative abilities. Such discussions create debates among learners organized by the teacher, bringing various viewpoints into confrontation. In these cases, learners themselves produce concepts, laws, and solutions while solving educational tasks.

Philosophy ensures that learners acquire theoretical knowledge across various fields while preparing them to navigate the current era of rapidly increasing information.

Consequently, all educational activities in philosophy require continuous improvement, and the teaching methodology must meet high standards.

For instance, philosophical education, based on the development of philosophical worldview, addresses several educational and upbringing objectives: it familiarizes learners with the dialectics of knowledge in theory and practice; it ensures the pre-planning and successful execution of experiments; it develops learners' scientific and research skills; it synthesizes scientific knowledge across all sections of the philosophy course into a unified system; it fosters learners' independent work skills; and it enhances learners' creative abilities [4, 112].

The renewal of society, the progress and prospects of our life, the independence of the country, and the development of socio-economic policies aligned with a market economy necessitate preparing competitive specialists who possess comprehensive knowledge and a modern scientific worldview. This, in turn, requires the continuous improvement of the content of education [5, 40–46].

The philosophical worldview of youth is formed based on their acquired knowledge of nature and society. Social realities in society are reflected in the individual's thinking, which constitutes their worldview. A student with a scientific worldview strives to understand laws based on concrete evidence. Reliable evidence is one of the essential tools forming the foundation of scientific worldview. For this purpose, evidence must be elevated to the level of theoretical generalization.

Scientific worldview expresses the general and specific features of numerous phenomena, while generalizations serve as explanatory and predictive units. Using theoretical generalizations, learners master the principles and methods of solving all tasks. Within the scope of worldview-expressing generalizations, methodological ideas and approaches occupy an important place because they reveal the inner laws of objective reality more deeply. Methodological ideas constitute the primary mechanism for mastering scientific knowledge. Therefore, the pedagogical process aimed at forming a scientific worldview should regularly introduce learners to methodological ideas. In this process, learners must assimilate several laws characteristic of dialectical cognition and synergetics. These include:

- Within the framework of philosophical worldview, a set of fundamental laws and principles must be assimilated by youth, including:

- The materiality of the world and its knowability;
- Motion as a form of existence of matter;
- The primacy of matter and the secondary character of consciousness;
- The unity and struggle of opposites;
- Cause-and-effect relationships as a general law of material existence;
- The transformation of quantitative changes into qualitative changes;
- Irregularity and regularity in development;
- Interconnectedness of causes and effects;
- Phenomena as expressions of existence;
- Practice as the basis of knowledge and the criterion of naturalness.

Within philosophical worldview, learners also form a number of core concepts and ideas, such as:

- The foundations of social development;
- The laws governing changes in socio-economic conditions;
- The role of cultural and societal development in the history of the Uzbek nation;
- Gradual development and the forces driving it;
- The global scope of scientific and technological progress and the key factors in the development of New Uzbekistan;
- The development of interethnic relations and the formation of civil society;
- The significance of state leadership and individual freedom in building a social state in Uzbekistan.

At different stages of education, the depth and level of an individual's worldview are analyzed using specific theoretical generalizations. In cultivating youth philosophical worldview, attention should be paid to helping them understand the interconnectedness of various phenomena. By forming a clear understanding of the relationships between events, learners can achieve a holistic perception of reality. Their pursuit of social and ideological-moral maturity is directly linked to their intellectual and scientific development.

During this process, some learners may exhibit uncertainty, narrow-mindedness, passivity, or insufficient political knowledge. In such situations, one of the key responsibilities of educators is to systematically equip youth with knowledge about societal life and socio-economic development.

G.P. Shedrovitsky's concept differentiates between learning as the process of assimilating social experience and educational-cognitive activity. Learning is incomplete assimilation, whereas educational-cognitive activity involves a specially organized assimilation associated with the use of learning tools. Educational-cognitive activity comprises content, learning outcomes, organizational processes, psychological functions, abilities, and assimilation processes [6, 248].

According to V.D. Shadrikov, learning is not a creative process directed at understanding the processes of existence, but rather the assimilation of culture accumulated by humanity, a form of "internalization" or "reception" [7, 51].

S.Yu. Jdanov emphasizes that educational-cognitive activity is not aimed merely at achieving results in specific types of activity but emerges as a theoretical and practical activity directed at self-assimilation. It is effective in mastering knowledge about the components of activity and the skills required to perform them [8, 81].

Renowned scholar E.F. Foziev, in his studies, considers the development of independent thinking and the engaging organization of the knowledge process as a creative source for achieving new successes in youth activities [9, 83]. E. Goziev's research explores aspects of managing students' educational activity, including planning, self-monitoring, self-assessment, defining human activity, goal-setting, and effective time management. To clarify these concepts, the scholar developed diagnostic methods for managing educational activity and examined theoretical and practical aspects of the relatively underexplored problem of learning activity management. Structured questionnaires, each containing over ten questions (sometimes with additional items), were used, taking into account individual characteristics of students. Discussions emphasized the etymology of key concepts, facilitating learners' acquaintance with the structural components of educational management. Recommendations

were also developed for teaching and learning processes, providing information on stages of self-awareness [10, 13].

Z.T. Nishanova developed a set of exercises aimed at fostering independent and creative abilities in youth. While the exercises focused primarily on forming cognitive operations, they also addressed the development of creativity in terms of speed, accuracy, and originality [11].

In the research of E.Z. Usmonova, the motivational-emotional regulation of thinking under conditions of intellectual conflict is examined. Usmonova emphasizes that shaping thinking requires attention to the content and organization of education, freedom in learning, and the use of various methods for solving creative tasks, which ensures learners' activity, critical thinking, efficiency, and sharpness of mind [12].

Ye.N. Kabanov-Meller identifies two dimensions of learning activity: thinking (the content-logical aspect) and observation, imagination, and sensory-emotional engagement. He considers learning activity as reflecting the educational tasks assigned to learners [13, 4].

N.A. Menchinskaya developed the principle of knowledge assimilation as the primary type of cognitive activity, identified the importance of teaching in human activity, and clarified its content and functions [14, 79]. M.Ya. Alekseeva notes that the foundation of students' cognitive activity is a complex learning process encompassing multiple mental processes (perception, memory, thinking), learners' attitudes toward the surrounding world, and personal qualities such as emotion, will, and intellect [15, 42].

N.F. Talizina divides cognitive activity into general and specific types. General cognitive activity includes planning one's own activity, monitoring its execution, and employing all methods of logical thinking (comparison, proof, classification, etc.) to work with knowledge across various domains. Specific cognitive activity includes only knowledge applied within a particular domain [16].

Analysis of psychological literature on cognitive activity leads to the conclusion that managing learners' educational-cognitive activity is implemented during the teaching of social-humanitarian, natural and exact sciences, general-professional, and specialized subjects, and provides the necessary conditions for their professional development.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a student's worldview manifests in the educational process through the values and moral norms they acquire. Their consciousness should fully reflect their way of life, allowing them to comprehend the essential aspects of existence and the meaning of values. For youth to internalize the fundamental norms of social life, they must have a clear understanding of human life and the activities that regulate it. Thus, their worldview also reflects their behavioral orientations. Any worldview is directed toward specific activities and possesses a degree of stability.

The formation of a scientific worldview in young people enables them to make informed choices regarding a healthy lifestyle. In interactions and collaborations with educators, students demonstrate their scientific worldview. This worldview serves as a benchmark for relationships that guide them toward a stable and purposeful life. Achieving this requires the assimilation of essential knowledge. A scientific worldview does not arise randomly; it is the result of acquiring specific knowledge and life experiences.

The modernization of society, progress and future prospects, the independence of the nation, and the formation of socio-economic policies compatible with a market economy necessitate the training of competitive specialists who are well-rounded, knowledgeable, and equipped with a modern scientific outlook. Ensuring the effectiveness of this process requires continuous improvement of educational content.

Philosophical disciplines, particularly philosophy itself, play a crucial role in shaping the worldview of youth. It is advisable to focus students' attention on key issues of worldview, such as the emergence of scientific research methods, the scientific understanding of the universe, and the practical application of scientific knowledge. For example, in teaching ontological perspectives of the universe, educators should direct students' attention to philosophical conclusions and worldly problems based on scientific knowledge and methodologies.

Students should be encouraged to engage deeply with questions that cultivate a scientific worldview, such as: "What is existence? How did it arise? How was the universe formed? What is the essence of life? What principles govern all events in the world?"

In summary, philosophical thinking and creative abilities emerge from social conditions and are realized through concepts, reasoning, and language derived from social practice. Although the origin of thinking lies in sensory perception, it transcends the mere reflection of sensation and allows humans to acquire knowledge about the real world—its objects, properties, and relationships—which cannot be perceived directly.

References:

- 1.Savelyev I.V. Course of Physics. Vol. 3: Quantum Optics, Atomic Physics, Solid State Physics, Nuclear and Elementary Particle Physics. St. Petersburg: Lan', 2016. – 308 p.
- 2.Leshukov A.P. Conceptual Foundations for Realizing the Worldview Potential in the Special Training of Future Physics Teachers in Pedagogical Universities. Doctoral dissertation, Vologda, 2003. – 265 p.
- 3.Purysheva N.S., Sharonova N.V., Romashkina N.V., Mishina E.A. Collection of Contextual Problems on Physics Teaching Methodology: Educational-Methodical Guide. Moscow: MGPU, 2016. – 116 p.
- 4.Sadriddinov N., Rahimov A., Mamadaliev A., Jamolova Z. Fundamentals of Physics Teaching Methods. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2006. – 245 p.
- 5.Tugalov F.Q., Bekmirzaev R.N. The Role of Natural Sciences in Shaping Students' Scientific Worldview (Using Physics as an Example). Pedagogy: Scientific-Theoretical and Methodological Journal. Tashkent, 2018, No. 4, pp. 41–46.
- 6.Systemogenesis of Educational and Professional Activity: Collection of Scientific Works of the IV All-Russian Scientific-Practical Conference Dedicated to the 70th Anniversary of V.D. Shadrikov. Yaroslavl: YSPU, 2009. – 227 p.
- 7.Shadrikov V.D. Activity and Abilities. Moscow, 2004. – 84 p.
- 8.Zhdanova S.Yu. Style of Educational Activity and Its Development: Based on Research of Philology and Mathematics Students. Candidate of Psychological Sciences Dissertation Abstract, Perm, 1997. – 94 p.
- 9.G'oziev E. Psychology: Youth Psychology. Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 1994. – 244 p.

10. G'oziev E., Jabborov A. Activity and Behavior Motivation: Educational Manual for University Psychology Specialization. Tashkent, 2003. – 124 p.
11. Nishonova Z.T. Psychological Foundations of Forming Independent Creative Thinking. Doctor of Psychological Sciences Dissertation, Tashkent, 2005. – 391 p.
12. Usmanova E.Z. Motivational-Emotional Regulation of Thinking under Intellectual Conflict Conditions. Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 1993. – 104 p.
13. Kabanova-Meller Ye.N. Educational Activity and Developmental Learning. Moscow: Znanie, 1998. – 4 p.
14. Menchinskaya N.A. Learning Problems and Intellectual Development of Students: Selected Psychological Works. Moscow, 1999. – 224 p.
15. Alekseeva M.Ya. Development of Cognitive Activity of Senior Students in the Process of History Education Based on an Individual-Diagnostic Model. Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences Dissertation, Moscow, 2004. – 213 p.
16. Talyzina N.F. Formation of Students' Cognitive Activity. Moscow, 2003. – 96 p.